

ISic3081

I.Sicily inscription 3081

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

accounts

Material

limestone (breccia)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2009.10.06

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Taormina, Antiquarium del

Teatro Antico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI331832

1. [— — —]INOY.ΕΜ [—]
2. [.c.6. .]κόσια τάλαντα [σ]ιτο[φυλάκοις] κ υ,α [—]
3. μων λοιπὸν
4. [— — —] τριάκοντα
5. σιτωνίῳ Φρύνιος [— — —]χίλια
6. [(?)έβ]δομήκοντα
7. [—] λοιπὸν
8. τάλαντα
9. [— — —]
10. ἑννέα ἐξήκοντα λίτραι [—]
11. [— — —]
12. [— — —]
13. σιτωνίῳ [—]
14. [— —] λοιπὸν
- 15.
16. ²columna (pagina) a dextra parte plane detrita est²
- 17.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645433

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Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 38.0973a

Manganaro, G. 1988. Le tavole finanziere di Tauromenion. In Knoepfler, D. (eds.), *Comptes et inventaires dans la cité grecque: actes du colloque international d'épigraphique tenu à Neuchâtel du 23 au 26 septembre 1986 en l'honneur de J.Tréheux*. Neuchâtel. pp. 155-190. At 155-156 ph

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